

ReBioCycle in a nutshell

ReBioCycle provides a portfolio of advanced bio-plastic sorting and recycling technologies for bio-based biodegradable plastics within **three complementary waste-processor-centric hubs** at a demonstration scale located in **Italy, Spain, and the Netherlands**.

The Hubs

These hubs operate in real-world environments to efficiently recycle three types of bioplastics: PLA, PHA, and composites. The Hubs will provide **Real-World Demonstrations** and showcase our novel recycling solutions.

Project coordinator

University College Dublin,
BiOrbic Bioeconomy SFI
Research Centre
Kevin O'Connor

Project duration

4 years
1 October 2024 –
30 September 2028

Visit our website
and our Social
Media channels:

www.rebiocycle.eu

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Circular
Bio-based
Europe
Joint Undertaking

Bio-based Industries
Consortium

Co-funded by
the European Union

ReBioCycle

A new European blueprint for circular bioplastics upcycling solutions

HUB Leader:

"The current recycling technologies available for recycling biodegradable plastics are limited, but with this project we are going to make them widely available. Then nobody can claim that the switch to biodegradable plastics cannot be made, because they cannot be recycled"

Jan Pels, TORWASH CTO.

Partners

NL HUB Material Flow Overview

 The Netherlands

The Dutch Hub will focus on chemical technology, upscaling it to TRL 6 and will be using TORWASH technology to recycle PLA and PHA polymers (500 kg each) and transform them into rPLA, and PBM to make PHBV from hydrolysed PHA and PLA. TORWASH leads the Dutch Hub.

Other partners and collaborators are the Dutch waste sorting, NTCP, the site owner and sorter, TotalEnergies Corbion, Paques Biomaterials, and Corbion will be involved. Kaneka Belgium is also supporting this hub.

Input:

PLA and PHA from sorted mixed plastics.

Processes:

Chemical recycling.

Outputs Available:

rPLA, PBM and PHBV

NL HUB Map

